

Studies on Phosphate Solubilisation by Microbes and Enrichment of Soils with Phosphates

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Continuous silting caused by the sedimentation of suspended solid particles carried by the river Ganga has adversely affected its normal flow causing irreparable damage to the ecosystem of the river. Extensive cost oriented dredging of the river beds together with proper management of different waste disposal is needed for the restoration of ecological balance of the river. However, enormous phosphate and other nutrient (like nitrogen) mobilisation have been observed in the sediment of the Ganga¹. The annual sediment transport of the Ganga is to the tune of 328 million tons². Phosphate mobilisation is also observed in the slurries of the sewage treatment and biogas plants.

Phosphate is known to be an essential nutrient for plants and animals. Phosphate fertilizers are extensively applied to increase soil fertility. However, due to solubility limitations, a major portion of the phosphate becomes immobilised and ineffective as insoluble inorganic and organic phosphate and therefore can be regarded as lost. It is desirable to try ways and means to solubilise a part of the phosphate present in the Ganga sediments (as well as in slurries from the sewage treatment and biogas plants) using its normal microbial flora (as biofertiliser)^{3,4} so as to make sediments and slurries agronomically effective as substitutes for phosphate fertilisers. The studies on the P-solubilising bacteria and the agronomic use of sediments were previously reported⁵⁻⁹. Milad and Salam⁷ found that the Nile sediment improved said moisture content, organic matter level, soluble phosphate and total nitrogen of desert sand soil making it suitable for plant growth.

El-Gabaly *et al.*⁸ reported improvement of the physical texture of sandy soil by Nile sediment. Sabet *et al.*⁹ indicated better nutrient uptake if soil management was done with fertiliser and the Nile sediment mixture.

These considerations led us to isolate a number of microbes capable of P-solubilisation from the sediments of the Ganga and study some of their properties. The results are described in this paper.

Results and Discussion

Sixteen bacteria were isolated in defined medium from the Ganga sediments. All of them were found to be Gram-positive having good phosphate solubilising activity as reflected in the formation of halozone around colonies. Solubilisation of phosphates was supposed to have started as soon as colony appeared but solubilisation activity was measured as a function of halozone formation against time.

Phosphate solubilisation activity of the isolates showed three distinct patterns. Group-I of isolates (4, 8, 9, 19, 12 and 13) (Fig. 1) were cocci and showed good activity. A linear rise of the microbial phosphate solubilising capability was observed upto 96 h of experiment without any initial lag or late stationary phase for isolates 4, 8, 12 whereas isolates 9, 10 and 13 showed an initial lag phase of 24 h. The activity of isolate 12 showed an intervening stationary phase from 48 to 72 h. This anomalous behaviour of the group can not be explained. Growth behaviour of these 6 isolates in sugar and sugar alcohol substituted medium varied quantitatively as

Fig. 1 Pattern of phosphate solubilisation by different isolates

well as qualitatively under the same set of experimental condition indicating positive differences among the isolates, at least at the strain level. Of these six isolates, 9 is quite different from the others as is apparent from its almost negative response to trehalose.

Group-II isolates (1, 3, 5, 14 and 15) (Fig. 1) consisting of mixed cultures of rod and cocci except 14 (cocci) and 15 (rod) exhibited a stationary phase after 72 h of linear growth with initial lag phase of 24 and 48 h for the isolates 14 and 15. Amplitude of growth of these five isolates under condition of sugar and sugar alcohol substitution varied markedly. Similarly, all the isolates showed differential preferences for substitution as well and this possibly indicates their separate taxonomic identity. In this group only isolate 15 can utilise fructose to a good extent.

Group-III (Fig. 1) comprises isolates 2, 6, 7, 16 (mixed cultures of cocci and rod and 11 (rod)) (Fig. 1). Here no halozone around colonies was observed within 48 h, even though the colony appeared as early as within 24 h, indicating late induction of solubilising process. After 48 h, all these isolates exhibited a rise in activity and then became stationary after 72 h of growth. Growth behaviour in different substituted medium showed intra-group differences. Inability to utilise xylose separates isolate 11 from the rest of this group.

Isolates of Group-I showed solubilisation of tricalcium phosphate. Isolate 4, a Gram-positive rod is superior to all the isolates due to its higher solubilising capacity.

Phosphate solubilisation, as is known, may be due to secretion of extracellular organic acid (particularly 2-ketogluconic acid which causes solubilisation of calcium phosphate due to chelation^{5,6,10}) or it may be due to extracellular enzyme secretion. However, no appreciable pH change was observed in broth culture of the isolates of Group-I indicating the possibility of calcium phosphate solubilisation due to enzyme secretion. But Group-III isolates showed appreciable pH changes, suggesting that solubilisation must be due to acid secretion by the microbes. It is to be noted that though the fall in pH is indicative of P-solubilisation, no such trend is observed in many cases and there is no correlation between P-solubilisation and fall in pH.

Preliminary investigations showed positive enzyme activity for Group-II and particularly for Group-I isolates. But, it is not possible to derive definite conclusion regarding enzyme activity from our limited study. Moreover, proper identification and characterisation could not be made.

Growth behaviour of all these isolates in sugar and sugar alcohol substituted medium varied widely (Figs. 2-4). None of the isolates grew well in sorbose and fructose substituted medium excepting isolate 7 which had a feeble positive response. In most of the cases the magnitude of growth was far less compared to that with glucose supplement except isolates 3, 15 and 16. Isolates 3 and 15 responded better in sucrose substituted medium, whereas isolate 16 preferred trehalose. Most of the isolates were

NOTE

Fig. 2. Growth behaviour of different isolates under condition of different supplements: (1) control (glucose), (2) xylose, (3) galactose, (4) mannose, (5) sorbose, (6) fructose, (7) sucrose, (8) trehalose, (9) sorbitol, (10) mannitol

found to grow effectively in pentose substituted medium. Better pentose utilisation was found with isolate 3, whereas galactose and mannose were preferentially used by isolate 16. We could not assess the impact of all these substitution on the induction of phosphate solubilising abilities.

The isolation and proper use of phosphate solubilising bacteria together with sediments from the river Ganga or slurries (from sewage treatment or biogas plants) will improve the fertility of soil and soil texture at a reduced cost, reduce the cost of desilting of the riverbeds and make the biogas plants economically viable. Moreover, there is sufficient low grade phosphate rock in India unsuitable for superphosphate production. But the use of the rocks to the acidic soils together with sediments containing phosphate solubilising microbes may ob-

viate the increasing demand of imported fertiliser.

Due to lack of resources and facilities, we could not proceed further. But intensive work in this direction together with the improvement of the isolated strains for their better adaptability and mineralising capability is highly desirable.

Experimental

The top soil samples of the river sediments were collected from the surface and at a depth of 10 cm at Naihati, Halisahar and Kalyani (West Bengal) and transported to the laboratory within 4-6 h. Appropriate care was taken to prevent secondary contamination. The soil sample (1 g) dissolved in sterile water (100 ml) and diluted to 10^3 ml. The solution was used as inoculum.

Individual colony was isolated by agar-plate dilution technique in sterile petri plates using phosphate solubilising bacterial medium¹¹ containing tricalcium phosphate (5 g) as insoluble phosphate. Other ingredients (in $g\ dm^{-3}$ of deionized water) were

Fig. 4. Legends same as in Fig. 2.

glucose, 10; $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 0.5; KCl, 0.2; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.0; yeast extract, 0.50; agar, 20; and traces of MnSO_4 , FeSO_4 . The pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.8. All the seeded petri plates were incubated at 37°.

All the glasswares and the medium were sterilised. Inoculation was done using Klenzaid-Laminar flow apparatus (in perfectly aseptic conditions).

The extent of phosphate solubilisation was measured as a function of halozone formation around each colony. The diameter of the halozone measures the extent of solubilisation. Formation of halozones by the isolated bacteria in medium containing rock phosphate instead of tricalcium phosphate confirmed that the microbes are phosphate solubilising in nature.

Qualitative screening of the microbes isolated was done by growing them under condition of different sugar and sugar alcohol supplements after withdrawal of the normal carbon source from the medium. Growth was measured turbidometrically using a Systronics 118 spectrophotometer at 540 nm. Morphology of the isolated bacteria was studied under microscope after gram staining.

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